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Leadership Styles of Choreographers vis-à-vis Commitment of Student-Dancers across various Higher Education Institutions in Luzon, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the relationship between leadership style of choreographers and commitment of student-dancers. Respondents for the study are from different HEIs in the entire Luzon. Data gathering has been conducted through online survey using LSQ and OCQ to 105 choreographers and 228 student-dancers. Frequency, mean, sum and standard deviation were used to describe the leadership styles of choreographers and the level of commitment of student-dancers, and Pearson-r to determine the relationship between leadership style and commitment. Results found out that most of the choreographers' leadership style is democratic, while the commitment level of student-dancers was found to be moderately high. Leadership style has no significant relationship commitment which accepts the null hypothesis tested in the study. Further investigation was recommended to deeply understand the relationship between leadership style of choreographers and student-dancers commitment. Lastly, based on the results of this study, programs were designed to enhance leadership skills of choreographers and the commitment of student-dancers. The result of this study brings new information in the existing study in leadership and commitment, but is highly significant as new knowledge in the field of dance research.

INTRODUCTION

In the past years, there were only few to none local studies in the Philippines that were conducted about leadership styles of different choreographers and their relationships to the commitment of student -dancers. Studies conducted internationally related to these components were all highly immense in the field of business, human resources, team sports and health, but only a few in dance education. After numerous attempts of searching for related studies locally which focus on the relationship between leadership style and commitment, the researcher found out only limited resources that can be used and that further investigation should be conducted, as dance research occupies a limited sector in Philippine scholarship (Villaruz, n.d. a).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Types of Leadership Style

The leadership style choreographers apply play an important role in the success of the entire dance troupe or organization. It is also emphasized that choreographer-dancer relationship is an important part of the recipe of a successful dance production. Relationship between the choreographer and artist is not comparable to any other creative process (De Keersmaeker, 2019). Being a leader is a vulnerable position – it opens the choreographer to criticism, but able to invoke positive change within the team. The commitment and passion to dance of the artists depend on the leadership style that the choreographer is using and applying to the entire dance troupe.

Authoritarian leadership refers to a leader's behavior asserting a very strong authority and control to all subordinates and demanding accepted compliance from them (Farh and Cheng, 2000). It is also called “intense

style” and “autocratic style.” It includes a directive and very demanding coach who prepares the group for any type of performance (Castillo et al., 2020). In general, authoritarian leadership has a negative connotation across different literatures (Wang, et. al., 2019). It is usually the most-practice leadership style and displayed behavior across different societies and organizations. It is dominantly used in the Asia Pacific, Latin America, and Middle East business organizations (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Leaders who use this style usually provide instructions that should be followed strictly by their subordinates without any complaints, and should be completed on time, as provided. Also, leaders of authoritarian leadership expect that employees adhere to high standards and punish employees for not doing their job properly (Wang et. al., 2013). Authoritarian leadership has been an interesting issue across all studies in the discipline whether it gives a better or worst outcome to the group. Extensive research has been conducted about this specific leadership style and it is depicted as destructive by verifying its negative influence to employees' outcomes (Wang & Guan, 2018), such as voice behavior (Li & Sun, 2015), team identification (Cheng & Wang, 2014), and task performance (Chan, et. al., 2012). Based on the study of González-García, et. al., (2019), it was found out that there are simultaneous positive and high scores on the authoritarian behavior of the players' coach. In contrary, the study of Calvo and Topa (2019) found out that authoritarian leadership style is least desired by the base soccer players, and implies less satisfaction from the players, and marginally and negatively predicted positive affect intensity during competition (González, et. al., 2020; Jony et. al., 2019; Kalu & Okpokwasili, 2018).

Laissez-faire leadership is also known as “delegative

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leadership,” which is a type of leadership style where leaders are hands-off and let the group leaders decide (Kendra, 2020b). It is a style of leadership which is built on trust (St. Thomas University Online, 2018). STU Online defined laissez-faire leadership in practice as where leaders leave the job to their subordinates to complete the task in a freely manner, without requiring strict policies and procedures. This represents a management approach where there is a leader that has been nominated and physically occupies the managerial position; but he or she has avoided and abandoned his or her responsibilities (Lewin, et. al., 1939; Hinkin and Schriesheim, 2008; Skogstad, Hetland, et al., 2014). Such manners may change subordinates’ performance for the worse in one of two ways: probability is decreased for future desired behavior and opening door for increased levels of undesired performance (VonBergen, 2012). In the recent years, researchers have found out that this is a type of leadership that leads to the lowest productivity among members (Anbazhagan & Kotur, 2014). As supported with the study of Muhammad and Kuchinke (2016) this leadership style showed negative relationship with the outcomes of the Pakistani bank employees’ performance in terms of effectiveness and satisfaction. Diebig and Bormann (2020) study found out that followers do not receive any support from their leader which have led to stress. Results from the study of Almarakshi, et. al., (2019) regarding laissez-faire and its effect to job performance found out that there is no significant relationship between the leadership style and job performance of the employee in a non-profit organization. Hinds (2019) findings showed that the perception of the employees toward leadership style, transformational and laissez-faire, had an effect on their commitment to the non-profit organization. Oyetunji et. al., (2019) result findings on the relationship of laissez-faire leadership style to behavior and performance of construction workers showed that, when laissez-faire is adopted as a leadership style on the construction site, it will lead to a negative correlation with the workers’ performance. This implies that, the more laissez-faire behavior is adapted and applied in a group, the more of the workers’ performance reduces. Synonymous with the study of Gameda and Lee (2020), laissez-faire leadership style had a significant negative relationship with task performance. Therefore, adapting this leadership styles need an assessment to all subordinates if they are highly capable and able to perform task without supervision.

Democratic leadership, also known as “participative leadership style,” is based on mutual respect. This leadership usually requires collaboration between the leader and the followers. By its very definition, this style invites every of their own input and contribution within a group who may not be otherwise be (or feel) represented. Democratic leadership has been established and widely used for years now by different leaders across different societies and organizations. Democratic leadership style fosters participation from the athlete when it comes to

the process of decision-making in connection to the entire group’s goals and methods (Tucker, 2017). When everyone’s concern is heard, followers tend to feel valued and the more they are integrated to the group. Several studies have been conducted on the positive and negative outcome of democratic leadership style across the globe. Benefits of democratic style are self-sufficient workers, highly motivated workforces, different ideas, strengthened public interest, improved creativity, freedom of expression, equal rights, and confidence from staff (Coft, 2018). On the contrary, the disadvantages of this style include excess time consumption in getting numerous opinions, results varied depending on the age and maturity of workers, indecision where optimal solutions are not merely present, and the difficulty in assuaging all workers (Khan et. al., 2015). This style works best if all staffs are highly skilled and competent, and eager to share their knowledge and ideas (Chukwusa, 2019). Chukwusa also emphasized that it is necessary to give the staffs adequate time allowing them to contribute to the development of an action plan and eventually cast their votes before implementation. As it was defined, it will encourage staffs to be part of the decision-making process and is useful in all time horizon (Iqbal et. al., 2015). Likewise, the study of Milan (2008) showed that there is a greater number of managers that are situated in the democratic manager style. In addition, Rafferty and Wyon (2006) found out that dancers would prefer democratic leadership style rather than autocratic. In the descriptive study of Kim and Pang (2019) using multiple regression to see the influence of leadership style to the intent of the artistic swimmers to continue, the results showed that democratic leadership is above the mid-point of the scale ($M = 3.00$), indicated a positive outcome and experience with their athletic career. Dolly and Nonyelum (2018) also supported democratic style on job performance where they have found that this style has a high positive result in the performance of librarian staffs in Port Harcourt, River State, Nigeria.

Commitment

Commitment plays an important role in the success of a dancer. It comes with an understanding that what dancers do outside the studio is synonymous with what occurs inside (Taylor, 2019). Furthermore, dancers with strong commitment to what they do and to the entire group will do anything that is necessary in order to perform to their highest level. Utilizing all the resources available and techniques provided to them may be of great help in the development of their performances. Dancers who are highly committed constantly seek and ask beneficial ideas from their choreographers or sources in order to contribute to the performance. These include simple practices while on break, performing warm-up before the entire work-out process, eating healthy diet, sleeping enough hours every day, and using more sophisticated ways such as utilizing psychological and physiological professionals in order to maximize their potentials, and alleviate weakness and injuries that may enhance

performance.

Furthermore, the study of Hallajy, et. al., (2011) showed that Transformational leadership with ($\beta=0.53$) and transactional leadership with ($\beta=0.44$) can predict athletes' commitment using systematic modelling equation (SEM). The results of the study of Yusof and Saybani (2013), indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership style of coaches, sport commitment ($r = .419$, $\beta = .478$, q value=.001), and athlete satisfaction of football players ($r = .386$, $\beta = .443$, q value=.001). Therefore, it can be concluded that transformational leadership behaviors can increase sport commitment and athletic satisfaction of high schools' football players. In the study of Saybani et. al., (2015) it also found out that there is a positive and significant relationship between coaches' leadership style (transformational) and sport commitment of Iranian high schools' football teams. It is also found out that transformational leadership style had a significant effect on affective commitment of employees of the fitness clubs (Lee and Cho, 2018). Likewise, in the study of Abasilim, et al. (2019) showed that there is a significant medium positive relationship between leadership style (transformational) and employee's commitment, whereas transactional leadership style has an insignificant small negative relationship with employee's commitment. Abasilim, et al. also added that laissez-faire leadership style has an insignificant small positive relationship with employee's commitment. The study also recommended that appropriate leadership style should be adopted in order to attain positive outcomes to the employees of Lagos State Civil Service Commission of Nigeria.

In this research, there were numerous related studies mentioned that were conducted in other areas and disciplines. The researcher acquired only limited research to dance due to a small number of researches that are highly immense in the field of dance education, leadership, and management. Extensive research in the field of dance education (particularly in these areas) are significantly important to conduct to fill the gaps in research to dance education. These can provide choreographers with insights and knowledge from the basis of results and interpretations and the significance of the application of leadership styles which may either heighten or not the commitment of student dancers that could have a great impact on their relationship and performance.

This study aims to determine the relationship between leadership styles of choreographers and commitment of student-dancers. International research in these areas is numerous but in different fields and industries. Dance research in the Philippines is limited as mentioned in the Philippine Scholar (Villaruz, n.d). Therefore, the findings of this study will be helpful for future research in dance education, management, and leadership in the local setting. In this, this study aims to answer the following research question: (1) How may the Leadership Style of choreographers be described? (2) How may the level of commitment of student-dancers be described?

(3) Is there a statistically significant relationship between leadership styles of choreographers to commitment of student-dancers? (4) and, what program can be proposed based on the study findings?

Null Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the leadership style of choreographers and student-dancers commitment.

METHODS

The entire research was quantitative in design, and correlational study which aims to determine if there was a significant relationship between the leadership styles of choreographers to the commitment of student-dancers. Adopted survey questionnaires were used to obtain the needed data. Inclusion and exclusion criteria have been set to ensure the validity of data from the tools and statistical treatment that were used in the study, therefore, purposive sampling was employed in the study. All participating HEIs in the Entire Luzon must have: (1) a dance troupe for at least two (2) years. For the choreographers, the respondent must have been working with the group for at least two (2) years or above, (2) within the age range of 25-50 years old, and (3) either male or female. All student-dancers' participants should (1) already been a member for two (2) years and above and they should be in their 3rd or 4th year, (2) within the age range of 21-26 years old, and (3) either male or female. Participants who haven't satisfied the criteria set by the research will be automatically ineligible to partake in the study. Raosoft Sample Size Calculator was used to determine the target sample size of respondents (from both choreographer and student-dancers' total population) with a high level of accuracy. The total population of choreographers is 135 and the target sample is 101 respondents, while the total population of student-dancers is 450 and the target sample size is 208. Both of these target samples have a 5% margin of error and 95% level of confidence.

The instruments that were used for the study are all open and free to use in the public, thus open source. There are two questionnaires floated to all participants: Leadership style questionnaire (LSQ) is an 18-item questionnaire developed by Northouse (2016) that describes the style of leadership a person applies which will be adapted for this study. Responses are recorded on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). For the scoring of the questionnaire, sum of the responses from items 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, and 16 (authoritarian leadership), items 2, 5, 8, 11, 14 and 17 (democratic leadership), and items 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 (laissez faire leadership). For the interpretation, the range of score has been modified to describe the leadership style. From 19.51-24 (Range), 15.10-19.50 (Moderately High Range), 10.51-15.00 (Low Range) and 6-10.50 (Very Low Range). Cronbach's Alpha for prior application of this questionnaire is highly reliable at .860 (Seeger, 2020). Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) developed by Mowday et. al. (1979), is a 15-

item questionnaire and was tested from a series of 2,563 employees from non-divergent organizations. Six questions focus on employees' affective or attitudinal commitment, and the other 6 questions are phrased negatively, and their coded in reverse. Responses were recorded on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree), and items that were negatively phrased are scored in reverse. In the original report of Mowday et. al. Cronbach's alpha ranged from .82 to .93, with a median of 0.90 (Liou, 2007). The researcher sent a letter of request addressed to the presidents or officers-in-charge of all HEIs in Luzon from different Local Colleges and Universities (LUCs), State Colleges and Universities (SUCs), and Private Colleges and Universities to allow the conduct of the study in their institutions. The letter was sent through an electronic mail. All select participants also received the electronic mail. Questionnaires floated via Google forms where participants can answer. Questionnaires were filled-up within 10-15 minutes. All data gathered from Google forms were exported to an excel file for analysis. After the data analysis, the excel file was encrypted with a password so the researcher has the lone personal access to it. Descriptive and correlation statistical treatments were utilized to analyze the data with the application of IBM SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, sum, mean and standard deviation scores were computed to describe the leadership styles of choreographers

Table 2. Leadership Styles of Choreographers

Leadership Style	Questions	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>Authoritarian</i>	1	3.19	0.92	Moderately High
	4	2.19	0.99	Low
	7	3.22	0.90	Moderately High
	10	2.86	0.90	Moderately High
	13	3.17	0.88	Moderately High
	16	3.46	0.80	Very High
	Total Score	18.08	3.54	Moderately High
<i>Democratic</i>	2	3.42	0.75	Very High
	5	3.17	0.92	Moderately High
	8	3.55	0.80	Very High
	11	3.53	0.76	Very High
	14	3.11	0.91	Moderately High
	17	3.46	0.82	Very High
	Total Score	20.24	3.72	Very High
<i>Laissez-faire</i>	3	2.59	0.92	Moderately High
	6	2.62	0.96	Moderately High
	9	3.33	0.87	Very High
	12	2.99	0.94	Moderately High
	15	2.59	1.04	Moderately High
	18	2.10	0.96	Moderately Low
Total Score	16.20	3.75	Moderately High	

choreographers. Based on the results, it was found out that most choreographers from various HEIs in Luzon who answered the survey questionnaire uses democratic leadership style which corresponds to "Very High Range" (M=20.24, SD=3.72), authoritarian leadership style ranks second with "Moderately High Range" (M=18.08, SD=3.54), and lastly laissez-faire leadership style which

Table 1. Point scale interpretation

Range of Weighted Mean	Description
3.26 – 4.00	Very High Range
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately High Range
1.76 – 2.50	Low Range
1.00 – 1.75	Very Low Range

and the level of student-dancers' commitment. For the correlation part, Pearson r was computed to test the relationship between choreographers' leadership style and student-dancers' commitment. To facilitate the analysis and interpretation of the data obtained, the researcher will follow the point scale interpretation to describe per item response for choreographers' leadership style and level of student-dancers' organizational commitment as shown to Table 1:

RESULTS

In order to get the results, IBM SPSS version 26 has been used to run all the data gathered from the respondents. A professional and experienced statistician processed all gathered data from the online survey which was done through Google form and exported to an excel file. The adapted questionnaires used for the study were answered by one hundred one (105) choreographers and (228) student-dancers from different HEIs in the entirety of Luzon.

Table 1 illustrates the leadership style of the

respondents to "Moderate Range" (M=16.20, SD=3.75).

The levels of commitment of student-dancers are described in Table 2. Based on the results, most of the respondents from various HEIs in Luzon are highly committed and willing to put great effort beyond normal expectations from them to help their respective dance

troupe (M=3.73, SD=0.56) and proud to be part of the organization (M=3.71, SD=0.61) which both corresponds to “Very High.” While on the other hand, decision to work on the dance troupe was definitely mistake on their part (M=3.22, SD=1.09) and little changes in the current circumstance of respondents will cause them to leave the dance troupe (M=2.74, SD=0.98) are both “Moderately

high.” Lastly, loyalty in the dance troupe (M=2.18, SD=1.14) and working on other organizations that is similar to their current task/work (M=1.96, SD=0.90) ranges “Low” and “Very Low” respectively. Overall, the general weighted mean on the level of commitment of dancers was found out to be “Moderately High” (M=3.16, SD=0.28).

Table 3. Commitment level of student-dancers

Questions	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>I am willing to put in great deal of effort beyond that normally expected in order to help the Dance troupe be successful.</i>	3.73	0.56	Very High
<i>I talk up the Dance troupe to my friends as a great organization to work for.</i>	3.60	0.67	Very High
<i>I feel very little loyalty to this organization.</i>	2.18	1.14	Low
<i>I would accept almost any type of role in order to keep working for the Dance troupe.</i>	3.57	0.65	Very High
<i>I find that my values and the dance troupe’s values are very similar</i>	3.33	0.69	Very High
<i>I am proud to tell others that I am part of this dance troupe.</i>	3.71	0.61	Very High
<i>I could just as well be working for a different organization as long as the type of work/task was similar.</i>	1.96	0.90	Very Low
<i>This dance troupe really inspires the very best in me in the way of job performance.</i>	3.66	0.61	Very High
<i>It would take very little change in my present circumstances to cause me to leave the dance troupe.</i>	2.74	0.98	Moderately High
<i>I am extremely glad that I chose this dance troupe to work for over others I was considering at the time I joined.</i>	3.55	0.66	Very High
<i>There’s not too much to be gained by sticking with the dance troupe indefinitely.</i>	2.57	1.07	Moderately High
<i>Often, I find it difficult to agree with the dance troupe’s policies on important matters relating to its dancers.</i>	2.57	1.05	Moderately High
<i>I really care about the fate of the dance troupe.</i>	3.62	0.64	Very High
<i>For me, this is the best of all possible dance troupe for which to work.</i>	3.47	0.69	Very High
<i>Deciding to work for this Dance troupe was a definite mistake on my part.</i>	3.22	1.09	Moderately High
General Mean	3.16	0.28	Moderately High

Table 4. Correlation between Leadership Style and Commitment

	Pearson Correlation	Authoritarian	Democratic	Laissez Faire	Commitment
Commitment		-.073	.012	-.049	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.460	.902	.617	
	N	105	105	105	228

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows the relationship between choreographers’ leadership style and student-dancers commitment. A Pearson r correlation was run to determine the relationship between choreographers’ leadership style and student-dancers commitment. As shown in the table, there was no significant correlation between choreographers’ authoritarian leadership style and student-dancers commitment, (r = -.073, p = .460). There was no significant correlation between choreographers’ democratic leadership style and student-dancers commitment, (r = .012, p = .902). There was no significant correlation between choreographers’ laissez faire leadership style and student-dancers commitment, (r = -.049, p = .617).

This study has some limitations. There are some Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Luzon which their performing arts organization or dance troupe is no longer operational or temporarily suspended, and will only be continued once pandemic is done which cause the data gathering from the target respondents difficult.

There are some participants who haven’t confirmed and declined their involvement in the study. Originally, the target population of this study only focuses on HEIs situated in region 3 or Central Luzon. Because there are only few respondents who answered the online survey questionnaire, the researcher anticipated that recruitment might not meet the target sample size for this study. In this, expansion in the scope of the population was performed while still focused on the target number of participants of the study for the statistical analysis to be used in the study will be valid and highly significant. This provided an opportunity for this study to cover respondents from different HEIs representing the entire Luzon.

DISCUSSION

Choreographers’ Leadership Style

In the description of choreographers’ leadership style approach, it was found out that the majority of the respondents who answered the online survey questionnaire applies democratic leadership style as their way to lead

the entire dance troupe which can be supported from the study findings of Coft (2018). This leadership style is very beneficial to all the members of the dance troupe (both choreographer and dancers) which can result to highly sufficient dancers, highly motivated workforce, diversified ideas that can be shared to everybody which can lead to creation of new and fresh concepts, strengthen the interest of the public or the entire organization, freedom of expression, equal rights, and highly confident dancers that may lead to a better and successful performance. On the other hand, acknowledging this positive response from the participants of using democratic leadership style as their approach towards to their handled artists, it should also be taken into consideration of the disadvantages of using this specific style, and it should be based upon the current situation (such as skill and competency), pressure level and level of commitment of members. It is stated in Chukwasa (2019) findings, that this specific leadership style can be applied if all the members of the dance troupe are already highly capable and competent, and able to share their knowledge to the entire group. Thus, this style may be of great help, if all the members of the dance troupe are already highly skilled and capable, meaning, they can be taught and supervised easily. However, if the case is different, then this style may not be effective or applicable.

Level of Commitment of Student-dancers

For the level of commitment of student-dancers based on the results, most of the respondents are highly committed to their dance troupe, but not necessarily extreme. It means that there might still be some gaps or needs, or factors affecting it, that should be addressed to further heighten their commitment. From the study findings of Aujla, et. al. (2014), enjoyment is the most important factor which correlates to commitment and other several sources curtailed to it such as emotional, social and physiological factors. There are also other factors that affect commitment which was based on the study findings of Suryani (2018) such as age, tenure in the organization, self-efficacy, culture, satisfaction and engagement. In all the related findings that are mentioned in this study, commitment is highly emphasized to play a crucial role in the entire performance of an organization. Highly committed dancers are strong-will and they will do whatever it takes in order for the entire organization to perform on its peak.

Relationship between Leadership Style and Commitment

Authoritarian Leadership Style and Commitment

In the relationship between authoritarian leadership style and commitment, it was found out that there is no significant relationship between the two variables. In the results found in this study, it did not support neither the positive and negative results from various studies across different disciplines related to these components. For instance, the positive relationship between the two variables, such as in the study findings of Al Khajeh (2018), Kalu and Okpokwasili (2018), Matiko and

Mbuti (2018), Chua et. al. (2018), NawoseIng'ollan and Roussel (2017) and Velu et. al. (2017a) that autocratic or authoritarian leadership style have a positive impact in the organizational performance and members' commitment. On the negative findings from various studies, Study of Essien and Ekoriko (2020) found out that autocratic or authoritarian leadership style has a negative influence on workers job retention and participation in decision making which is related to the employees' commitment. Autocratic or authoritarian leadership style is found out to contribute demotivation and job dissatisfaction to highly competent and committed project workers (Hassan and Ismail, 2020). Zhao and Sheng (2019) found out that there is a negative correlation between authoritarian leadership with employee, engagement, and a negative correlation with vigor and dedication which are all determinants of commitment. In the study of Jerome (2018), it was found out that the level of job satisfaction of library was low, since the most practice leadership style of the supervisor is authoritarian. Also, in the study findings of Afsar (2014) where authoritarian leadership style has a negative influence in the affective commitment of university faculty members of Pakistan. Synonymous with the study findings of Leng et. al (2014) shows that when the leader performs autocratic or authoritarian leadership style, an adverse impact can affect retail employees' commitment. Most of the studies that were found regarding the relationship between these two variables are highly on the negative connotations and its disruptive effects, and few on its positive effect to people across different disciplines. However, the result from this study is still not proven in the area of dance research. Further investigation in connection in these two variables is highly recommended.

Democratic Leadership Style and Commitment

The result of this study found out that there is no significant relationship between democratic leadership and commitment. Most of the related studies that were found has positive connotation about this specific leadership style. This leadership style has a lot of positive effect to the commitment of the members of an organization which was contradicted by the result of this study as it has no significant to each other. Democratic leadership style has been established and widely used for years now by different leaders across different societies and organizations. Democratic style of leadership has a significant influence on the innovativeness, task performance, retention and participation in decision making of the workers which results to high organizational commitment (Essien and Ekoriko, 2020b). In the study of Zaidi and Rao (2020) revealed that there is a significant association between perceived leadership style, specifically democratic approach, to the organizational commitment of Tourism SMEs. Democratic leadership style of the managers as perceived by their employees has a significantly positive impact on their organizational commitment (Rai and Budhathoki, 2020). Assefa (2020) study revealed that there is a significant relationship between democratic leadership style and teachers school

commitment. Study findings of Alvi et. al. (2020) found out that democratic leadership shows a significant positive impact on the performance of employees where commitment does mediate the relationship between this style to performance. Democratic leadership style has a strong confirmatory impact on the organizational performance which is a result from highly committed members (Jony et. al., 2019). In the study findings of Diana et. al. (2021), Setiawan et. al. (2021), Dike and Madubueze (2019), Al Khajeh (2018), Wachira (2018), and Matiko and Mbuti (2018a) it was found out that democratic leadership style elicits higher level of trust, and leads subordinates to reciprocate through exhibiting higher level of organizational performance. Study of Khaliq et. al. (2016) found out that there was a positive effect of participative and supportive leadership behavior and the organizational commitment of employees in the Education sector of Pakistan. These are conclusive results based from various studies determining the relationship between this specific leadership style to commitment which can result to better performance from the members of the organization. However, based on the result of this study, it suggests to further investigate the relationship between the two variables in the same setting and discipline.

Laissez-faire Leadership Style and Commitment

It was also found out that there is no significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style to commitment. The result of this study supported by the findings of Tadese (2019) where there is no statistically significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and organizational commitment. Study of Matiko and Mbuti (2018b) also supported the findings of this study that there is no significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style to commitment among Government Hospitals Employees in Dodoma City, Tanzania. Gardner (2018) study findings revealed that there is a weak but no significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and organizational commitment of Government Contract Employees. The study findings of Zeleke and Yeshitila (2015) also revealed that there is no significant correlation observed between laissez-faire leadership behavior to organizational commitment which was conducted at Defence University. The finding of this study is somehow contrary to some of the studies that were conducted regarding the relationship between the two variables. Some studies resulted to either positive or negative correlation. Such as in the study findings of Harb et. al. (2020) where the results revealed that there is a positive correlation between laissez-faire and commitment of middle managers working in public administration in Lebanon. Study of Lanier (2020) also revealed that laissez-faire leadership style plays a prominent role in the organizational commitment of Telecommunicators. Dim and Nzube (2020) study findings also revealed that laissez-faire leadership style has a significant positive effect in the performance in a foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

It was also found that laissez-faire leadership style and other leadership styles (e.g, democratic or participative, and transformational leadership) have a greater influence on employees' work performance and can increase job satisfaction, commitment and performance (Kesse, 2020). Study of Amini et. al. (2020) also found out that laissez-faire increases the level of commitment of employees in Afghan Wireless Communication Company (AWCC). On the negative findings based from different studies in connection between this specific leadership style to commitment, Laissez-faire or also known as avoidant leadership had negative and significant effect on job satisfaction which is also a factor that affects commitment (Nweke et. al., 2021). There is a lesser significance in the relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction of employees from the banking sector of Pakistan (Iqbal et. al., 2021) which is consider as a factor that curtails to commitment. In the study of Robert and Vandenberghe (2020) it was found out there is a strong negative indirect effect of laissez-fair leadership style on affective commitment. In the study of Ekpenyong (2020), it was also found out that there is negative correlation between laissez-faire leadership style to employees' performance which is from the result from the commitment of employees in a business organization. A negative correlational relationship was also revealed between laissez-faire leadership style and employee job satisfaction which is considered as one of the factors that affects commitment (Henry et al., 2019). Study of Sitsiyan, et. al. (2019) also found out that there is no significant relationship between laissez-faire to performance and commitment. There may be studies that can support this study; however, these are based from other disciplines. The result of this study is still considered not conclusive, and further studies in relationship to these two variables in the field of dance research can be conducted. Overall, the relationship between leadership styles of choreographers and student-dancers commitment, it was found out that there is no significant relationship between the two variables accepting the null hypothesis of the study. The result of this study contradicted the findings of Abasalim, et al., (2019), Saybani (2015), and Saybani (2013) who found out that there was a statistically positive relationship between leadership style and commitment. One of the limitations of these findings, it only focuses on three well-known leadership styles introduced by Lewin, et. al (1939). There are other leadership styles that were introduced and applied by different choreographers. It further suggests that other leadership styles that were not mentioned to this existing study may be added to deeply understand the relationship between the two variables. Lastly, the results of this study are not conclusive. Further investigation regarding the relationship between these two variables is highly recommended.

CONCLUSION

After obtaining the data from 105 choreographers and 228 student-dancers through an online survey, it was

found out that most of the choreographers in the entire Luzon apply Democratic as their style of leading their dance troupe. On the level of commitment of student-dancers, the results showed that most of the respondents are highly committed and lastly, for the relationship of the two variables, it was found that there was no statistically significant relationship between leadership style and commitment accepting the null hypothesis formulated by the researcher. In the result findings on the correlation of leadership style and commitment, the researcher concluded that dancers may still be highly committed regardless of what leadership style is being implied by the choreographer which contradicted a lot of existing studies. Even the findings of this study resulted in no significance between the two variables, results will still be respected and further investigation can be recommended.

Recommendations

- Although previous studies have shown that democratic leadership style is an effective way to lead and supervise people, this further suggests, as stated on the discussion part, the addition of other leadership styles which are not mentioned in this study. Another feasible recommendation is to organize leadership and management development or training programs from professional individuals of various industries and also from the field of dance which are highly beneficial to choreographers handling dance troupes. These activities may be part of the program of the office (e.g., Office of Student Affairs, Support Services Office, etc.) which supervises the dance troupe. These training and development programs may provide knowledge such as important points from the most recent and trending style/s based from professionals' experiences handling different types of people. Additionally, what specific leadership style or combination of two or more that can be applied and practiced by the choreographers to their handled dance troupe based on its needs that may greatly develop the commitment of student-dancers to the organization and can improve choreographer-dancer relationship. From what Abasilim, et. al., (2019) have stated on their findings, appropriate leadership style is highly recommended to attain positive outcomes and strengthen the commitment from the members of the organization.

- In connection to the commitment of student-dancers, based on the result findings, the study recommends that the office that handles the dance troupe should organize activities such as team dynamics or team building exercises to be part of their support program, that focuses on the commitment and role of the members to dance-troupe. But before providing activities such as these, the office or the choreographer shall observe and take note of all the problems, demands or factors that need to be addressed and prioritize which highly affects the commitment of student-dancers. These types of activities are very beneficial for each member of the team for they will be able to know and understand each other, and to set clear goals for the entire organization's

development and success. Also, these activities teach people to work together, thus improving choreographer-dancer and dancer-dancer relationship, improves morale and engagement, increases productivity, foster innovation and creativity which all can result in intensified and highly committed dancers.

- Based from the results of relationship of leadership style and commitment, the study recommends and suggests that additional variables (mediating or moderating variables) such as the demographic profile (e.g., gender, age, years of experience, etc.) of choreographers and factors affecting the commitment (e.g., age, tenure in the organization, etc.) of student-dancers may be added to this existing study to further determine its relationship or effect. Also, applying a mixed-method with a combination of interview, observation and survey is also recommended to deeply understand choreographers' point of view of their leadership style and student-dancers' level of commitment to dance troupe.

- For the proposed programs for leadership and management of choreographers and commitment of student-dancers, all Higher Education Institutions in Luzon, Philippines may adopt or modify the programs based on the needs of their respective dance troupes.

- This study only focuses on Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) duly accredited by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in Luzon and does not embody the entire community of choreographers and dancers. To represent the entire population, this study may be expanded by adding respondents from the basic education under the supervision of the Department of Education (DEPED) who are handling performing arts, dance troupes or dance club/organizations, and also other dance groups (e.g., street dance crews, non-profit organizations, etc.) outside the supervision of these two agencies, of the same setting and scope for future studies, and confirm if the results will be similar.

Results of this study is very significant as this provide new data from the existing studies across different disciplines and additional information in the body of science pertaining to leadership and commitment, but is highly noteworthy most especially in the field of dance research since there are only few studies conducted related to leadership and commitment in the Philippine or local setting.

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APPENDIX

Proposed Program Designs
Proposed 2-Days Leadership Training and Management Program/Workshop
<p>Overview:</p> <p>Team Building exercises will strengthen and build the whole team while developing the members of the dance troupe; it helps people steer away from blame and create a climate of commitment, loyalty and support. This training program aims at aiding choreographers understand the various elements that go into building and managing an effective team.</p>
<p>Program Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain why teamwork and intra-group cooperation are essential to effective and success performance of a dance troupe. • Introduce basic management models, leadership styles, motivational techniques and the concept of participatory decision-making. • Understanding of various team roles and how to harness the different strengths and styles to improve team performance. • Reflection of one’s own role and preferred style in a team. • Effective feedback.
<p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <p>The purpose of this two-day workshop is to transfer skills and lessons to the choreographers’ respective dance troupes that they are handling, so that effective leadership style and team work will become a hallmark of the dance troupe.</p> <p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <p>The purpose of this two-day workshop is to transfer skills and lessons to the choreographers’ respective dance troupes that they are handling, so that effective leadership style and team work will become a hallmark of the dance troupe.</p> <p>The following are the specific outcomes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide information, knowledge skills and resources on team building and demonstrate the importance of teamwork in the development and success of the dance troupe. 2. Apply and practice appropriate leadership style which can result to positive outcomes and commitment development of the members of the dance troupe. 3. Inculcate skills on leadership and decision making. 4. Explain methods of dealing with dance troupe’s conflicts, including resolution and third-party mediation. 5.Lay out a plan of action to address identified development capacity to improve dance troupe’s overall performance.
<p>Methodology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The two-days workshop will utilize the following methods\ - Presentations - Facilitation - Small group sessions - Large group discussions - Mental games and exercises -Physical games and exercises
<p>Training Aids</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flipchart and flip stand - Markers - Overhead projector and screen - Laptop/Computer - Writing Paper - Tape - Training notes
Proposed Agenda
Day One

Topic and Content	Objectives	Activities
INTRODUCTION (60 minutes)	General Training Objectives:	
Preparations for the Training A. Host B. Venue C. Training Workshop Area D. Participants, Groupings, and Roles E. Facilitator Pre-Training Phase Training Phase Post-Training Phase F. Syllabus	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To develop the knowledge, capability and attitudes of participants for effective leadership. To provide a better understanding of organizational mechanisms and equip participants with certain skills on organizational management. To provide the participants with a forum for interactive exchange of experiences, insights and lessons on leadership and organizational management. To equip participants with knowledge on doing leadership work To provide basic information needed for the management of projects and activities for their respective organizations. To acquire and learn more methods for effective facilitation. 	Input Discussion
BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT (60 minutes)	Specific Objectives	
A. Introduction of participants and facilitators B. Sharing of participants' expectations C. Identification and discussion of needs and concerns of participants D. Presentation of the training objectives and design E. Common context and situation of the participants	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To get to know the participants and facilitators, their expectations and training needs. To link the participant's expectations to the overall training objectives and design. To understand the general situation their respective dance troupes and the particular situation of members/artists in the institution of the participants, as a background and context for the training. 	Show and tell Expectation Check Workshop Discussion Input
LEADERSHIP (120 minutes)	Specific Objectives:	
A. Meaning of Leadership B. Traditional Leadership C. Modern Leadership D. Developing the Positive Aspects of Traditional and Modern leadership E. Guiding principles of People-centered Leadership F. Principal Leadership Tasks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To study and understand the kinds of leadership in order to guide the participants in the promotion of Dance troupe members' development. To deepen the participants' understanding of people-centered leadership principles and tasks that they can apply and practice in the management of their performing arts organizations. To improve the participants' capabilities to facilitate leadership training seminars in their respective organizations and localities. 	Picture analysis Story-telling Role Playing Workshop Input Discussion Buzz Session
Day Two		
Topic and Content	Objectives	Activities
Organizational Management (120 Minutes)		
A. Definition of Organization and organizational management B. Characteristics of a strong and stable organization (Dance troupe) C. Structure of an Organization (Dance troupe) D. Running Meetings and facilitation E. Planning, implementation, monitoring and assessment F. Resolving conflicts within the organization (Dance troupe)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To acquire an overview of the knowledge needed to run an organization (dance troupe). To gain skills in organizational management. To learn how to distinguish between organizations that serve the interest of the majority and those that serve the interests of the self-interested view. 	Group dynamics Role playing Story telling Workshop Input Discussion

Organizational Development and Management of Projects and Activities (180 minutes)		
A. Development Orientation B. Project Management C. Steps in Planning D. Implementation E. Evaluation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To understand what is organizational development and to differentiate the kinds of development projects and programs being implemented in the organization (dance troupe). 2. To understand project and activity management as an essential part of organizational development and achievement of the organization's general objectives. 3. To enhance understanding of the interrelationship of planning, implementation, assessment and evaluation in the whole activity and project management process. 4. To upgrade the participants' skills in facilitating and managing projects and activities in their respective organizations (dance troupe). 	Group Dynamics Lecture Group Discussion Workshops Buzz Word
Facilitation Skills and Methods (120 minutes)		
A. How to Facilitate B. Points of the facilitator to remember or consider C. How to ensure systematic management of Trainings or discussions D. How to become a better facilitator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To equip the participants with the necessary knowledge and skills for effective facilitation. 2. To provide instructions, reminders and helpful tips to keep in mind while facilitating training sessions. 	
Proposed Commitment Enhancing Program		
<p>Overview: Team Building exercises will strengthen and build the whole team while developing the members of the dance troupe; it helps people steer away from blame and create a climate of commitment, loyalty and support. This training program aims at aiding choreographers understand the various elements that go into building and managing an effective team.</p>		
<p>Program Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance dancers' self-discipline and appreciation of the role of leadership by building mutual trust and confidence. • Build team cohesion by breaking barriers in interpersonal relationship. • Improve dancers' internal attitudes and proactive behavior to function as a team with motivation and cooperation. • Help dancers to assess critical factors in dance troupe performance and more deeply explore how the entire group can effectively capitalize on group resources. • Heighten the commitment of dancers in the dance troupe. 		
<p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly committed and motivated members of the dance troupe. • Developed interpersonal skill. • Appreciative of the role of the choreographer and its leadership style to the overall dance troupe's overall performance. • Highly informed and guided dancers of their roles and responsibilities as members of the dance troupe. 		
<p>Training Aids:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cones - Webbing - Tossables - Large cards (1 deck) - Poster board - 3x5 Cards (25) - Pens - Markers - Easel Pad - Small tarps (2) -Hula Hoops (4) 		

--Clipboards (8) - Cards for partner draw - Mousetraps (10) - Blindfolds - Chiji Cards (Other Cards if not applicable)	
Proposed Agenda	
Day One	
Introductions - Overview of the Program	20 minutes
Warm up activities/Name of Games 1. Everybody is it- <i>warm up activity</i> 2. Thumb in the hole- <i>Warm up get to know activity</i> 3. Group Juggle- <i>name game</i> 4. Hand Shakes- <i>warm up/introduction skills</i> 5. Card shares- <i>Get to know you activity</i> 6. Debriefing/Large Group Discussion	Duration: 60 minutes Objectives • To create an environment of belongingness. • Formation of group bonds • To lessen the tension and anxiety of members being in the team • Learn each other's name and characteristics • To challenge and bring the members of the dance troupe outside of their comfort zones where can learning can take place.
Full-Value Contact 1. Goal Setting (Individual and Group) 2. Introduction to Full-value contact 3. Norms and Behavior Development 4. Create groups full-value contact 5. Debriefing/Large Group Discussion	Duration: 60 minutes Objectives • To set the norms and standards that the dance troupe will follow to allow them to reach their individual and group goals. • Allow members to channel and be part of the decision-making and the creation of these norms. • To develop a sense of ownership from dance troupe members of the program they are participating in. • Teaching responsibility of the entire dance troupe and individual to hold up what the group has deemed of value
Initiative 1: TEAM WORK 1. Magic Carpet- <i>teambuilding/communication</i> 2. Helium Hula Hoop- <i>cooperation/problem solving</i> 3. Partner Draw- <i>communication</i> 4. Debriefing/Large Group Discussion	90 minutes Objectives • To inculcate the significance of working as one team in accomplishing goals. • Cooperation vs. Competition • Think <i>WIN WIN</i> • Bring the dance troupe members out of their comfort zones in the growth zone.
Initiative 2: TRUST 1. Trust Walk- <i>Introduction of Trust</i> 2. Mousetrap Circle Activity- <i>the importance of trust/how emotions affect others</i> 3. Mousetrap Partner- <i>Defuse negative feelings safely (The entire members of the dance troupe will work as one to this last trust activity. All members must show that they are prepared for this activity through how they were able to handle the first two activities. Not all the groups will be prepared to proceed to this activity. The overall outcomes of this specific activity will not impact other activities.)</i> 4. Debriefing/Large Group Discussion • Chiji Card Debrief - An activity where we reflect all the activities we did in the workshop and how these important lessons be applied to our daily lives and for the rest of the entire program. - Goals for the program.	90-120 minutes Objectives • To learn to trust one self and show others that you are trustworthy. • To propagate trust among the group in order to operate as one team. • To take responsibility of one's feelings.